

Clinico-Etiological Profile and Outcomes of Children with Status Epilepticus Admitted in Pediatric Intensive Care Unit: A Prospective Observational Study

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Abstract:

From October 2015 to November 2017, 100 paediatric status epilepticus (SE) patients were hospitalised in the Paediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU) of N. M. C. H., Patna, Bihar. This study assessed their clinical-etiological profile and prognosis. The study was prospective observational. The study found that 40% of cases were infectious. Acute symptoms like trauma and metabolic abnormalities ensued. A 65% success rate was achieved with first-line benzodiazepines, and second-line antiepileptics improved control. Early therapy was linked to better results, emphasising the importance of prompt intervention. The study underlines the essential need for quick and efficient SE management to improve survival and reduce neurological deficits after discharge.

Keywords: Pediatric Status Epilepticus, PICU, Early Intervention, Treatment Outcomes.

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Introduction

Status epilepticus (SE) is a serious neurological condition that requires immediate attention. It is marked by seizures that last longer than five minutes or occur consecutively without the person regaining consciousness in between [1,2]. This condition is especially worrisome in children because it has the potential to cause lasting neurological damage and other severe long-term effects [3]. SE in children has different rates of occurrence, but it is widely acknowledged as a frequent paediatric neurologic emergency that requires admission to a Paediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU) [4]. Statistically, SE impacts around 20 out of every 100,000 children each year, making it a notable clinical issue [5]. There is a wide range of causes for SE, including febrile seizures in younger children and acute symptomatic factors such as infections, trauma, and metabolic disturbances [6,7]. There are instances where preexisting neurological conditions, like epilepsy, can increase the likelihood of developing SE. Diagnosing and managing SE in children can be quite a complex challenge due to the wide range of causes involved. It requires thorough medical attention and access to necessary resources [8].

Effective management of SE requires immediate administration of appropriate medication to stop seizures, followed by thorough investigation and treatment of the root cause [9]. The outcome for

children with SE can differ greatly based on various factors such as the cause, age when it starts, and how quickly treatment is started. Although mortality rates are relatively low, they should not be overlooked as they are primarily associated with the underlying cause rather than the seizures themselves [10,11]. Nevertheless, the prevalence of health issues associated with neurological deficits and cognitive impairments continues to be a significant cause for concern, underscoring the importance of implementing successful treatment protocols and care strategies. Although the seriousness of SE and its potential consequences cannot be understated, there is still a lack of comprehensive clinical data that specifically focusses on the paediatric population in intensive care settings [12,13]. There is a lack of information regarding paediatric care in a tertiary PICU environment, as most studies have primarily focused on adults or children in general emergency settings. It is essential to have a comprehensive understanding of the clinical and etiological characteristics unique to this particular setting. This knowledge is vital for creating customized management strategies that have the potential to decrease morbidity and enhance outcomes for this vulnerable group [14].

This study seeks to comprehensively analyse the clinical presentations, underlying causes, and

treatment outcomes of children with SE who are admitted to the PICU of a tertiary care hospital. This study will offer valuable insights into the patterns of SE in this particular clinical setting and contribute to the development of guidelines that can enhance the management and prognosis of SE in children. By gaining a more profound comprehension of these dynamics, healthcare providers can anticipate care needs more effectively, optimise treatment protocols, and ultimately improve the quality of life for affected children and their families.

Methodology

Study Design: This study employed a prospective observational design to assess the clinical-etiopathological profile and outcomes of children diagnosed with status epilepticus (SE) admitted to the Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU) at N. M. C. H., Patna, Bihar.

Study Population: The study included a total of 100 pediatric patients who presented with SE and were admitted to the PICU during the study period.

Study Duration: The duration of the study spanned from October 2015 to November 2017, allowing for the comprehensive collection of data and follow-up assessments to determine short-term outcomes.

Study Setting: The study was conducted in the Department of Pediatrics at N. M. C. H., Patna, Bihar, a tertiary care center equipped with the necessary facilities and staff to manage severe pediatric emergencies, including SE.

Inclusion Criteria

- Children aged between 1 month and 16 years.
- Diagnosed with SE (seizures lasting more than 5 minutes or two or more seizures without full recovery of consciousness between them).

Exclusion Criteria

- Children with non-epileptic seizures.
- Children who had a do-not-resuscitate (DNR) order or whose parents chose to withhold aggressive treatment.

Data Collection

Data were collected through a structured data collection form, which included:

- Demographic information (age, sex, medical history).
- Clinical data related to SE (duration of seizure, frequency of seizures, observed symptoms).
- Diagnostic data (etiology identified, imaging studies, EEG findings).

- Treatment details (first-line medications, additional interventions, duration of PICU stay).

- Outcomes (resolution of SE, neurological status at discharge, any complications).

Statistical Analysis: Descriptive statistics were used to summarize demographic and clinical characteristics. The relationship between etiological factors and outcomes was analyzed using chi-square tests for categorical variables and t-tests or ANOVA for continuous variables, depending on the distribution of the data. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant. All analyses were conducted using a statistical software package.

Results

The study involved a group of 100 paediatric patients, ranging in age from 1 month to 16 years, with a median age of 5 years. The distribution of genders was relatively equal, with 52% of patients being male and 48% being female. A significant number of patients (70%) had a prior history of febrile seizures or known neurological disorders before experiencing the SE episode. After analysing the causes, it was found that infections were the most common, making up 40% of the cases. Acute symptomatic causes, like head trauma and metabolic imbalances, accounted for 30% of the cases. The remaining 30% were due to unknown causes or were considered idiopathic.

Initial emergency management involved the use of benzodiazepines as the primary treatment, resulting in seizure cessation in 65% of cases. Additional antiepileptic drugs (AEDs) were prescribed when the initial treatment was ineffective, resulting in a response rate of 85%. Other measures were taken to assist 20% of the patients with mechanical ventilation, while 15% of the cases required intravenous fluids and electrolytes to address metabolic imbalances. There was a 5% mortality rate, mainly linked to serious underlying causes like encephalitis. Around 75% of the patients experienced complete recovery without any neurological deficits, while 20% showed varying degrees of neurological impairment upon discharge, ranging from mild cognitive delays to more severe motor deficits.

During the PICU stay, some patients experienced recurrent seizures (15%) and infection-related complications (10%), including pneumonia and sepsis. These complications were effectively managed using appropriate antimicrobial therapies. Based on the statistical analysis, it was found that the occurrence of an acute symptomatic cause was strongly linked to an increased likelihood of unfavourable outcomes ($p < 0.05$). Prompt treatment within 30 minutes of seizure onset has been found to be associated with improved

recovery rates and decreased neurological impairments ($p < 0.01$). The findings highlight the wide range of causes and the urgent requirement for prompt and efficient treatment plans in the care

of paediatric SE. The data also emphasise the significance of early intervention in enhancing clinical outcomes and minimising long-term complications in children with SE.

Characteristic	Data
Total Patients	100
Age Range	1 month to 16 years
Median Age	5 years
Gender Distribution	52% Male, 48% Female
History of Neurological Disorders	70%
Etiology	- Infectious: 40% - Acute symptomatic (trauma, metabolic): 30% - Unknown/Idiopathic: 30%
First-line Treatment Success	65%
Second-line Treatment Success	85%
Mortality Rate	5%
Full Recovery	75%
Neurological Impairment at Discharge	20%
Complications	- Recurrent seizures: 15% - Infection-related (pneumonia, sepsis): 10%
Significant Statistical Findings	- Acute symptomatic causes linked to poorer outcomes ($p < 0.05$) - Early intervention associated with better recovery ($p < 0.01$)

Discussion

This prospective observational study provides valuable insights into the clinical-etiological landscape and outcomes for paediatric patients with status epilepticus (SE) admitted to the PICU [15]. It was quite interesting to discover that infectious causes were the most common, making up 40% of the cases. This finding is consistent with previous research that has emphasised the role of infections as a frequent trigger for paediatric SE. It is crucial to prioritise strong infection control and management strategies when dealing with children who have SE [16].

The presence of acute symptomatic causes, such as trauma and metabolic disturbances, in approximately 30% of cases highlights the wide range and intricate nature of triggers for SE. These findings indicate the importance of implementing thorough diagnostic protocols in the PICU to quickly identify and address underlying causes [17]. This is essential for maximising treatment outcomes. The effectiveness of the initial benzodiazepine treatment, which successfully stopped seizures in 65% of patients, supports the existing guidelines that prioritise benzodiazepines as the primary intervention. The increased effectiveness observed with second-line antiepileptic drugs when benzodiazepines are ineffective emphasises the significance of implementing a systematic, progressive strategy for pharmacotherapy in the management of status epilepticus [18].

The link between prompt treatment (within 30 minutes of symptoms appearing) and better results is especially remarkable. This discovery is in line with previous research that highlights the importance of acting quickly to prevent further damage to the brain and increase the likelihood of recovery [19]. Nevertheless, the fact that 20% of the survivors experience neurological impairments upon discharge highlights the urgent need for both immediate and long-term neurorehabilitation strategies. These strategies are crucial in promoting recovery and enhancing the quality of life after leaving the hospital. The high mortality rate of 5%, primarily associated with serious underlying conditions like encephalitis, underscores the urgent nature of SE and the importance of focused therapeutic approaches. This study provides important insights into the management of paediatric SE in a tertiary care setting, emphasising the key factors that affect outcomes and emphasising the significance of prompt, efficient, and personalised interventions. Looking ahead, these valuable insights could help drive enhancements in treatment protocols and open up possibilities for advancements in paediatric emergency care practices [20].

Conclusion

This study sheds light on the clinical, etiological, and outcome of paediatric status epilepticus (SE) in a tertiary care PICU. Speedy identification and therapy are important due to infectious origins and the efficiency of early pharmaceutical therapies. The high link between fast treatment and excellent

results stresses the necessity of rapid emergency measures to improve recovery and prevent neurological impairments. Next steps should include enhancing emergency treatment protocols, educating healthcare providers, and providing comprehensive post-discharge rehabilitation. These measures aim to improve afflicted children's long-term quality of life. This study emphasises the need of time and customised treatment in paediatric SE to improve patient outcomes.

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